

PROPERTY TAX REVENUES OF LOCAL GOVERNMENTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA ACCORDING TO THE LEVEL OF DEVELOPMENT¹

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Abstract: This paper focuses on the share of property taxes in local revenues of Serbian local self-government units in the period 2011-2019, while local self-government units are classified into four groups according to the level of economic development measured by the regional GDP per capita. The results show, that the shares of property taxes on local revenues increased during the monitored period 2011-2019 and are higher in more developed areas of Serbia. We can also point to the unneglectable break in our time series, which is observed in 2013 when Serbian municipalities answered to changes in legislation with a dramatic increase in property taxes to load their budgets with missing resources.

Key words: Local government, local tax, property tax, economic development

JEL code: H71

INTRODUCTION

Public sector and public finance reforms were realized in almost all democratic countries in Europe. Emphasizing fiscal federalism and fiscal decentralization, special attention was paid to the local public sector and local financial management. Promoting the increase of efficiency in the overall public sector, the Theory of Fiscal Federalism (Oates 1972, 1999) recommends shifting one of the three basic public finance functions to the local governments. However, we mean the allocation function, which covers the wide field of public goods.

The decentralization of the allocation function of public finance requires expenditure, as well as revenue decentralization. In case of the revenue decentralization, the local self-government should be able to manage its revenues, too, with a certain degree of financial autonomy. Many authors (e.g. Stegarescu

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2005, Liberati and Sacchi, 2013; Bird 2015) stress, that financial autonomy is determined by taxes where local self-governments dispose with tax power. The OECD taxonomy of tax autonomy (OECD, 2020) accentuates the taxes where local self-governments are granted the set tax rate and the tax base independently (or it is set forth in the appropriate legislation). In many countries, including the Republic of Serbia (or Serbia), the property tax fulfills these characteristics and presents an important instrument for shaping the local tax policy.

However, the empirical evidence shows, that the revenue from the property tax in local budgets is eclipsed by revenues from shared taxes and transfers in EU countries (Maličká, 2017), and in Serbia, too (Randjelovic and Vukanovic, 2021). As Serbia is on a path to maintaining sustainable economic growth and sustainable public finances, the overall modernization of both private and public sectors has been realized since the 2000s. The legal framework of fiscal decentralization introduced in 2006 and 2007 included also property tax decentralization. Serbian local self-governments have had this instrument of local tax policy at their disposal since 2007. The brief insight into local budget revenue dynamics shows, that in case of the revenue insufficiency as a direct consequence of the global financial crisis and the central government's peculiar interventions (Bartlett, Đulic, and Kmezić, 2020), Serbian local self-governments proceeded to its active exploitation, and our observation is supported by Kmezić (2016), too.

The paper aims to examine the portion of property taxes in local revenues of Serbian local self-governments and its dynamics in the period 2011-2019 which covers the abovementioned economic and political turbulences. Besides, the evident unequal development of the regions was the motivation to include the aspect of the economic development measured by the regional gross domestic product per capita (GDP pc), which classifies Serbian local self-governments into four (five, respectively) groups. The time series does not cover external shocks presented by the beginning of the global financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemics, but obviously, it covers other important induced structural breaks. Taking this into account, the tests of structural changes (breaks) were provided to complete the insight into this period of financial management at the level of the local self-governments in Serbia.

1. INSTITUTIONAL BACKGROUND

Property taxes belong to primary direct revenues of Serbian local self-governments together with local (administrative, municipal, and sojourn) taxes,

certain fees for utilization of public goods, concession fees and other fees in compliance with the law, voluntary local taxes, certain monetary penalties, revenues from lease of real estate, interest rates earnings, donations, etc. Besides primary direct revenues, local self-governments in Serbia benefit from ceded revenues and transfers from the central government level (Law on Local Self-government Financing, 2006, Article 5). However, the current arrangement of the local financial management is a result of wider reform processes in Serbia.

At the beginning of the 21st century, the Republic of Serbia (RS or Serbia), like many other European countries a few decades before, decided to run the way of restructuring the public sector, too. It included administrative and fiscal decentralization, so it had a direct impact on the functioning of Serbian local self-government. The most important laws defining the local self-government in Serbia are the Law on Local Self-government (2007), Law on Territorial Organisation (2007), Law on Local Self-government Financing (2006), and Law on the Capital City (2007). The Law on Local Government Finance adopted in 2006, coming into force in 2007, introduced two crucial novelties. First, it made the inter-governmental transfer system more comprehensible and transparent, which allowed the local self-governments to plan their revenues. Second, the property tax decentralization was implemented, when local self-governments were granted the taxing power in property taxation. Local self-governments gained the autonomy in determining the tax rate within the range set forth by the appropriate law and the right to administer the tax themselves (Kmezić, 2016).

Authors focusing on the fiscal decentralization of Serbia (Đulic, 2016, Kmezić, 2016, Radoslavljević, 2017) mention the turnover in the decentralization of the public sector in Serbia. Radoslavljević (2017) sees a breakpoint in 2011. Until 2011 he regards fiscal decentralization as successful, after 2011 he describes the situation as “wandering what to do” with the local self-government in Serbia. According to Đulic, (2016), and Kmezić, (2016), the tendencies toward decentralization and fiscal decentralization respectively were obvious from 2000 up to 2008, and centralization and so-called pseudo-decentralization were observed since 2009. Although the Law on Local Government Finance worked on behalf of local self-governments, the global financial crisis (GFC) has stopped all its efforts and forced the central government to re-arrange the fiscal relations in the country (Bartlett, Đulic, and Kmezić, 2020). Similar activities of the central government could be observed in other European countries, too, e.g. Slovakia, where due to the GFC, the central government has legislatively reduced tax

revenues of municipalities and regions to generate additional resources in the state budget (Maličká, 2021).

Against the potential success of the local sector in Serbia, the turbulent period of the GFC had been replaced by another turbulent era pronounced by many legislative changes in the transfer funding and wage taxes (Kmezić, 2016; Radoslavljević, 2017). Instant and unpredictable cuts in local revenues made by the central government of Serbia encouraged the local-self-governments to raise property taxes to generate an additional source of financing for the local needs. This effect is observable as an evident bounce between 2013 and 2014 (see Fig. 1). One can consider it as a structural break and we can find some support also in Radoslavljević (2017), who admits a structural change in the time series after 2011, too.

The local self-government system in Serbia consists of municipalities, towns/cities, and the City of Belgrade. According to the Law on Territorial Organisation of the Republic of Serbia (2007), a municipality is a basic territorial unit where the competencies of local self-government are exercised, it has at least 10,000 inhabitants and a town/city is a territorial unit that has over 100,000 inhabitants (Law on Territorial Organisation of the Republic of Serbia (2007, Article 11 and 17). The special status of the capital city is specified in the Law on the Capital City (2007).

There are 145 municipalities in total in the territory of the Republic of Serbia and 29 towns/cities including the capital city. They are spread over the area of Central Serbia, the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, and the Autonomous Province of Kosovo, which unilaterally proclaimed its independence in 2008.

Fig. 1: LSGUs' revenues in 2011-2019

Source: Authors, based on the database of the Analytical Service of the Serbian LSGUs (2022)

2. RESEARCH BACKGROUND

In 2014, the regions in Serbia were classified into developed and underdeveloped regions according to the value of GDP pc in the region concerning the Republic of Serbia average. Consequently, Serbian local self-government units (LSGUs) are classified into four groups (I-IV) with a special sub-group within group IV (group IVa). Table 1 shows the classification of LSGUs in Serbia according to the Decree on establishing a single list of development levels of regions and the local self-government units for 2014 (2014). It classifies 145 LSGUs with the exclusion of 29 LSGUs in the territory of the Autonomous Province of Kosovo and Metohija.

Tab 1: Structure of LSGUs revenues in 2011-2019

	No. of LSGUs	% of total LSGUs	Development level as % of the RS average (100%)	
Group I	20	13.8	>100%	Developed
Group II	34	23.4	80%-100%	Underdeveloped
Group III	47	32.4	60%-80%	Underdeveloped
Group IV	44	17.2	<60%	Extremely underdeveloped
Group IVa (sub-group)	19	13.1	<50%	Extremely underdeveloped devastated areas

Source: Authors, based on the Decree on establishing a single list of development levels of regions and the local self-government units for 2014 (2014)

The further analysis excludes also the capital city which seems to be an outlier (and the LSGUs in the autonomous province of Kosovo and Metohija due to unavailable data). The research is using the data from the database of the Analytical Service of LSGUs.

The share of the property tax on local revenues of Serbian LSGUs is calculated for each of four (five, respectively) groups in the period 2011-2019. For testing the structural changes in the time series of the share of the property

tax on local revenues of each group of municipalities, we Andrews – Quandt test, the modified Chow test, for a structural break at an unknown point with 15 percent trimming as the first (supF test also known as Quandt likelihood ratio test for a structural break at an unknown point; Null hypothesis: no structural break) (Chow, 1960; Quandt, 1960; Andrews, 1993). To confirm our results, we use Bai-Perron multiple breakpoints and stability test (Bai and Perron, 1998).

3. PROPERTY TAXES ACCORDING TO THE LOCAL DEVELOPMENT

The dynamics of the shares of the property taxes on local revenues of Serbian LSGUs in four groups according to the level of economic development in the period 2011-2019 are projected in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Share of the property taxes on local revenues of Serbian LSGUs in % in 2011-2019

Source: Authors, based on the database of the Analytical Service of the Serbian LSGUs (2022)

An important increase of the property tax portion in total local revenues of Serbian LSGUs is observed after 2013, and it is more evident in the case of more

developed Groups I-III, which tend to resort to the more intensive usage of the property tax in the period 2011-2019.

Observed break in a time series underlies further statistical analysis on structural changes. Andrews supF test and Bai-Perron test are performed in this question. Unfortunately, the limitation of this part of the analysis is tied to the length of the time series and we admit a certain possible bias. However, the existing empirical literature (e.g. Kmezić, 2016; Đulić, 2016, Radoslavljević, 2017, Bartlett, Đulic, and Kmezić, 2020) support our results that point to a structural break in the time series on the property tax's portion on total local revenues in Serbia. Table 2 presents the results of the test for structural breaks. The recapitulation of the structure of Serbian LSGUs revenues in 2011-2019 is given in Appendix Table A. The structure of Serbian LSGUs revenues in 2011-2019 according to the level of development is shown in Appendix Table B.

Tab 2: Tests for structural breaks

	All the LSGUs	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV	Group IVa
Andrews test (supFtest) for Structural Breaks						
p-values	< 2.2e-16	< 2.2e-16	< 2.2e-16	< 2.2e-16	3.844e-06	3.725e-13
Optimal segment (m+1)-partition	3-seg. Partition	2-seg. partition	3-seg. partition	3-seg. partition	2-seg. partition	3-seg. partition
Number of breaks (m)	2	1	2	2	1	2
Breakpoint at observation number	3;6	3	3;6	3;5	4	3;5
Corresponding to breakdates	2013; 2016	2013	2013; 2016	2013; 2015	2014	2013; 2015
Bai-Perron Multiple Break and Stability Test						
BIC for number of breakpoints (m)	m=0 47.867	m=0 49.632	m=0 49.864	m=0 47.438	m=0 37.281	m=0 27.6248
	m=1 24.142	m=1 25.622	m=1 29.221	m=1 24.909	m=1 27.244	m=1 11.5982
	m=2 22.598	m=2 26.419	m=2 28.280	m=2 21.442	m=2 28.467	m=2 10.3975

	m=3 27.914	m=3 30.358	m=3 34.229	m=3 22.362	m=3 31.408	m=3 14.5561
Optimal (m+1)-segment partition	3-seg. Partition	2-seg. partition	3-seg. partition	3-seg. partition	2-seg. partition	3-seg. Partition
Number of breaks (m)	2	1	2	2	1	2
Breakpoint at observation number	3;6	3	3;6	3;5	4	3;5
Corresponding to breakdates	2013; 2016	2013	2013; 2016	2013; 2015	2014	2013; 2015

Source: Authors, own processing

The results of tests reveal multiple breakpoints in the case of the sample including all the Serbian LSGUs and in the case of Groups II, III, and IVa, where besides the evident breakpoint in 2013 (with one exemption in Group IV, where the breakpoint is shifted to 2014) other breakpoints are present, too (see Table 2, breakdates). This mirrors an optimal 3-segment partition or optimal 2-segment partition of the time series. Both Andrews supFtest and Bai-Perron test give us the same results. In the case of Bai-Perron test, the Bayesian information criterion (BIC, know also known as Schwarz information criterion) provides us with information on the optimal number of breakpoints, where lower values of BIC are preferred. As it was mentioned hereinbefore, during the monitored period, the central government eroded local fiscal capacity in achieving macroeconomic stability. According to the empirical evidence, the breakpoint in 2013 refers to a property tax reform coming into force in, 2014, by which the construction land use charge was abolished, and property taxes became more relevant (Kmezić, 2016). The indication for the next breakpoint in 2016 (2015 respectively) might be explained by the observed increase in another part of Serbian LSGUs' revenues, i.e. transfer funds (see Fig. 1 and Appendix, Table A and B).

CONCLUSION

Many authors stay, that during the monitored period 2011-2019, after the GFC, the central government in Serbia eroded local fiscal capacity by the unpredictable intergovernmental fiscal policy intending to achieve macroeconomic stability (Bartlett, Đulic and Kmezić, 2020; Kmezić, 2016).

Serbian LSGUs activated themselves in generating additional resources from the property tax to compensate for the unexpected cuts in their revenues. This paper examines the portion of property taxes in local revenues of Serbian local self-governments and its dynamics in the period 2011-2019. At the base of the analysis of the dynamics and concerning the classification of LSGUs according to their economic development, the paper test structural breaks in the time series of the property tax portion in local revenues.

The results of provided analyses point to the overall increase of the property tax's portion of total local revenues of Serbian LSGUs. An important structural break is observed in 2013, and it is more evident in the case of more developed groups of LSGUs, which tend to resort to the more intensive usage of the property tax in the period 2011-2019. Statistical tests on structural breaks revealed a breakpoint in 2016 (2015 respectively), too, which might be explained by the observed increase in transfer's portion in Serbian LSGUs' revenues. However, longer time series would provide us with more plausible insight into the analysis of the structural changes. It could be a perspective inspiration for further research.

Appendix

A: Structure of LSGUs revenues in 2011-2019

All the LSGUs	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Personal income tax	32.9	41.3	40.3	36.9	35.4	35.0	35.5	35.2	37.2
Property tax	7.8	6.7	7.8	12.0	13.1	12.6	13.3	13.6	13.7
Transfers and donations	24.1	25.1	25.3	25.1	24.7	24.5	27.0	26.8	26.0
Other ^a	35.2	26.9	26.6	26.0	26.8	27.9	24.2	24.4	23.1

Note: ^a Taxes, fees, and other revenues.

Source: Authors, based on the database of the Analytical Service of the Serbian LSGUs (2022)

B: Structure of LSGUs revenues in 2011-2019 in groups of LSGUs according to the level of development

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
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Group I									
Personal income tax	37.0	48.0	47.1	43.9	42.6	39.6	42.1	42.0	43.9
Property tax	9.4	8.2	9.7	14.9	15.5	14.2	15.4	15.8	16.0
Transfers and donations	13.8	11.8	11.5	11.6	10.8	10.8	13.2	13.9	14.2
Other ^a	39.8	31.9	31.7	29.6	31.0	35.3	29.4	28.3	25.9
Group II									
Personal income tax	35.8	44.6	44.1	38.7	37.3	37.7	38.8	37.5	38.9
Property tax	8.3	7.0	7.9	12.3	14.1	13.6	14.8	14.7	14.2
Transfers and donations	21.9	22.0	21.7	20.5	20.4	21.5	22.4	23.5	22.4
Other ^a	34.0	26.5	26.3	28.6	28.2	27.1	24.1	24.3	24.5
Group III									
Personal income tax	27.5	35.9	34.6	31.8	30.2	31.0	29.8	30.1	31.5
Property tax	6.0	6.0	6.8	10.7	12.0	12.1	12.3	12.9	12.8
Transfers and donations	33.8	34.2	35.6	35.7	35.7	35.8	37.5	37.4	35.6
Other ^a	32.7	23.9	23.1	21.8	22.2	21.1	20.3	19.6	20.1
Group IV									
Personal income tax	24.4	26.5	25.3	23.4	22.1	23.1	21.8	22.3	24.9
Property tax	5.6	4.0	4.9	6.2	7.5	7.7	7.3	8.1	8.8
Transfers and donations	44.7	53.1	53.1	54.0	51.1	51.4	54.2	53.0	50.0
Other ^a	25.2	16.4	16.7	16.4	19.3	17.9	16.7	16.7	16.3
Group IVa									

Personal income tax	20.8	22.0	21.6	19.8	18.7	20.4	19.1	16.8	21.8
Property tax	2.8	2.4	2.8	4.0	4.2	4.6	4.7	4.2	4.9
Transfers and donations	48.1	55.9	56.0	57.2	56.5	56.5	58.5	51.7	54.9
Other ^a	28.3	19.8	19.6	19.1	20.6	18.5	17.8	27.4	18.4

Note: ^a Taxes, fees, and other revenues.

Source: Authors, based on the database of the Analytical Service of the Serbian LSGUs (2022)

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